

EVALUATING TQM IMPLEMENTATION IN TEACHER EDUCATION THROUGH PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS' LENS: A CASE STUDY

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Article History

Keywords: Total Quality Management (TQM), Teachers Perceptions, Teacher education, Qualitative study

Article History

Received on 27 May 2026

Accepted on 19 June 2026

Published on 28 June 2026

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Abstract

Future teachers training plays a key role in teacher education institutions. But many challenges face teaching and management like poor quality in teaching and management. When we used method to improve business quality through better process teamwork and customer focus then we talk about the method of (TQM) total quality management. So the other side we started to apply this system in our educational institutional systems. However in Pakistan City like Sialkot how can teachers see or know about TQM in their own work or daily practices. They know very little about it. This study aims to find teacher perception about TQM practices in teacher education institutions of Sialkot. This study helps out their perceptions of TQM understand and suggestions for improvement. Through this qualitative study I will use semi-structured data method 10 in-depth interviews of experienced teachers from selected institutions in Sialkot. Those interviews recorded with the consent of participants or permission and data analysis using thematic analysis to find common patterns and themes. Expected fine to show both strengths and weaknesses in TQM practices like teamwork issues resources and leadership sport issues but teachers may suggest how we can apply better TQM practices in a better way. The findings help to enhance teacher training guide institutions leaders and to increase the quality of education in Pakistan. Although these results may inform the policies maker to which factor may help to improve TQM better perform institutions in national wide.

Introduction

Quality matters in every sector but in education quality matters a lot. Effective teachers training helps out the smarter students so in Pakistan context teacher education institutions prepare the future teachers. However let's quality standards outdated methods and poor management behind the scene of this struggle. These are the reason behind how teachers well performed (TQM) in their classrooms effectively. On the other hand TQM is a solution. TQM started where the same to improve products and services by facing continuous improvement, teamwork, customer satisfaction, and efficient process in the business world. It has five primary principles customer focus, total employee involvement, centred process thinking, integrated system and fact-based decision making.

Some past studies show that TQM works well in the education field. For example, The United States, and Europe found in his studies. Those schools using the through method apply and TQM had higher scores and satisfactory teachers (Sallis, 2014). TQM improves teaching quality standards and helps to reduce source ways in higher education (Sahney et al., 2024). Some TQM studies in Pakistan schools and universities show these benefits by Iqbal (2015) In Lahore University study tells us TQM has some issues in leadership but somewhere students and teachers are satisfied and boosted up. Another by Khan (2018) some public colleges tell us TQM practices helped in how resources are utilized in a better way? However these type studies data collection approaches are based on survey based approaches used. They are focused on university level not on teacher education specifically (Mahmood et al., 2021; Mahmood & Ismail, 2022).

This situation shows a gap in teacher education institutions. Although TQM shows effective results and promise, about how teachers perform effectively in education institutions. But we gain less knowledge about TQM. What their perceptions and thoughts apply well in their institutions? What challenges did they face? Existing study basically shows teacher perceptions of TQM practices in teacher education institutions in smaller cities like Sialkot Punjab.

A huge amount has teachers training colleges in Sialkot what last research about teacher's perception explores about TQM practices such as

leadership, staff training, or improvement of the support process(Khan et al., 2023; Mahmood & Ismail, 2022). Answer we research only score and give facts but they did not fill the gap behind "why" teachers feeling the most important question behind the gap how do teachers understand TQM in daily practices? What do they suggest this better perform in their daily practices? Without such questions research study incomplete and not fulfil problems gab.

So this study fills this cab we may apply a qualitative approach which aims to teacher's perception of TQM in teaching education institutions in Sialkot city of Punjab. We glad data through semi-structured interviews because interviews approach to uncover detailed views, teams and suggestions by teacher perceptions and their voices. The research will strengthen, weaknesses and to improve TQM. This study may have to improve leaders and teachers training programs policies also.

Literature Review

TQM concepts are very important in educational institutions and increasingly grow day by day in the field. Because it plays an essential role in quality education for national development. Basically it is derived from the industrial and business sectors that focus on continuous improvement, teamwork, leadership, customer satisfaction, and overall effective organizational processes. After passing time it is a compulsory where do you need in educational institutions to improve teaching quality performance and student outcomes. Where TQM team to gain an environment which lead future teachers to receive quality training through proper planning effective leadership, continuous improvement in their field at professional development opportunities.

Between 2020 and 2025 studies highlight that TQM positively affects their practices in educational institutions worldwide according to (Khan et al., 2023). An education institutional positively improved when TQM apply in their education sectors effectively their engaging teachers involvement and focus on continuous improvement. Similarly (Joseph et al., 2017) told us that achieve better outcomes academic performance better communication and strong teamwork among school staff members when TQM principles apply to their organization or educational institutions. On the other side we talk about higher education sectors where TQM has belonged with institutional

accountability and improved student satisfaction study explained by (Ferdousi, 2022) significantly two quality education improved in universities when that continuous evaluation staff development and student feedback outcomes contributed. Although reported found in a study of improve teaching standards and more engaging classrooms practices make when institutional has strong quality insurance in their places.

Particularly quality management required in every teaching educational institution because they prepare future education which later affect school systems and students learning outcomes. So according to (Carney, 2022) teachers development programs must require TQM India practices and must insure continuous professional growth in teaching practices and effective leadership support. So that total quality management provides us a framework basically which helps us to achieve our goals by continuous development, collaboration, engagement effective leadership, and systematic evaluation?

In implementation of total quality management in underdeveloped countries focuses on several challenges including limited resources, lack of training, resistance to change, institutional support. A South Asian research study demonstrates that although institutions recognize the importance of quality management, implementation remains constant in their educational context (Andary & Prabowo, 2025) now if we talk about Pakistani educational context struggle frequency remain the same with infrastructural problems, workload pressure, lack of professional programs opportunities which directly affect quality improvement efforts.

Frequently, Pakistani studies mainly focus on universities and school education rather than teachers institutions especially for example(Khan et al., 2019; Naqvi & Naz, 2025) highlight in Lahore study TQM ensure their practices when institutional engagement and teacher satisfaction in higher education institutions. And other Pakistani study demonstrate that quality insurance mechanisms such as student outcomes, evaluation, feedback system, teacher training programs positively and directly influence educational outcomes. At last year studies apply several methods and did not deeply explore the experiences of teachers, and your perceptions. Recent a Pakistani study also emphasized that teacher's involvement plays a significant role in

any successful detail and practices. According to (Ahmed & Suhag, 2024) study who actively participate in improvement initiatives demonstrate higher motivation and stronger commitment towards quality institutional goals. Although (Akram et al., 2024) study emphasized that the problem of leadership sport and the source availability are crucial factors for achieving educational quality goals in the teaching development centre.

Internationally outcomes based education (OBE) has linked to a TQM approach strategies which is emerged as significant quality improvement principles studies between 2020 and 2024 from Malaysia, Turkey, and Saudi Arabia indicate that (OBE) systems. Which helps to improve teaching quality, students competencies true evaluation and continuous improvement processes in any educational institution (Chandramohan et al., 2022). Furthermore, margin total quality management approaches in educational institutions used digital monitoring system, student performance, evaluation tools, which show the strength increasingly (Ai Tran et al., 2025; Mahmood & Ismail, 2022). Argued that digital system quality education based system improved transparency, accountability and communication administrations in teaching quality.

Despite these development researches remain sufficient because focusing on teacher education institutions in the small city of Sialkot, Pakistan. This study journal examines educational Management rather than teachers lived experiences about TQM practices. So, many researchers focus only on measureable outcomes rather than teachers understanding experiences, and respond to quality management systems in their daily practices. Therefore the teacher suggests that TQM has a significant role in any institution to improve potential teacher's motivations engagement, but this is possible without the success of leadership support teacher involvement continuous improvement and effective implementation strategies.

Statement of the Problem

In Pakistan especially in Sialkot teacher education institutions may face major issues. In which include outdated teaching methods, limited resources, and weak management. All these methods are factors that create big issues for teachers. They do not properly work in their field after gaining such training by improving the process of teamwork, and focus on students as customers,

could fix these problems through (TQM) total quality management. But leaders may apply these methods without knowing what the teacher thinks or feels?

The primary issue has deeply studied teacher's deeply real views on (TQM) in their institutions. Survey studies focus only on numbers but these studies do not work on personal stories individual's perceptions and feelings. But when we talk about a small city like Sialkot teachers already suffer with local challenges like shortage of funding and workload in their work places. Without understanding such questions the method never properly applies and we never know about strengths and weaknesses of (TQM) and never improve institution quality. This gap has a major effect on teacher's practices, students learning qualities, and overall education system in Pakistan context.

Significance/ Rational of the Study

This study plays a fighter role because this research gives us teacher's perception and their feelings about TQM and first time attempts in the Sialkot teacher education context. By selecting a qualitative approach to uncover hidden problems and their solutions. This study has to institutions leaders will give practical suggestions to strengthen TQM like better training and utilized resources, this research also raises standards about teachers, it highlights not only issues also supports and motivation level in their institution and boost up and job satisfaction. This study meets global standards and gives ideas to policy makers finding and shaping national guidelines for TQM in teacher's education institutions. It provides qualitative insight to the mostly survey-based studies in Pakistan. Which provides inside for future researchers and opens a new door for future work. TQM means super white better quality schools facilitate teachers work in a smarter way and a brighter future for students. Overall this study highlights the "why" and "how" to make real change.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to drive the essence of teachers lived experiences and perception of (TQM) total quality management practices in teacher education institutions in Sialkot City of Punjab.

1. To identify key TQM practices as perceived by teachers in these institutions.
2. To explore teachers' lived experiences of strengths and challenges in applying TQM.
3. To uncover common themes in how TQM affects teaching quality and institutional processes.
4. To gather teachers' suggestions for improving TQM implementation.

Research Questions

Overarching Research Question

What is the essence of teachers' lived experiences and perceptions of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices in teacher education institutions in Sialkot?

Sub-Questions

1. What key TQM practices do teachers observe in their institutions?
2. How do teachers experience the strengths of these TQM practices in daily work?
3. What challenges do teachers face when TQM is applied in their institutions?
4. How does TQM influence teachers' work, teaching quality, and student outcomes?
5. What suggestions do teachers have for improving TQM practices in teacher education?

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative case study to export teachers' perceptions of total quality management and also practices in education institutions in Sialkot, Pakistan. This approach was elected because it allows an in-depth understanding of participants lived experiences, first man views and challenges in applying TQM and also gathering suggestions for improving TQM implementations in their natural settings. This method is most suitable for achieving the objective school of my study and it focuses in depth detailed data. Dad cannot be measured through numbers alone. Research

methodology design focus on perspective teachers in education institution in Sialkot which is the city of Punjab with the help of this design I have explored the total quality management practices within a real education context. My data collection audience consists of 10 participants from education institutions. Among them are teachers, lecturers, and education officers. This year they lived experience according to their range of experiences with the maximum experience with being 15 years for the one participant.

Beside that for my data analysis in the study which I apply automatic analysis approaches. In this procedure identify the common pattern and themes that emerged from the participant responses. After data collection multiple times I carefully reviewed Dad information after then categorized it and drove the themes. Although this approach helped me extract the participant in those perceptions which are directly connected to the research questions and objectives of my study. The teams that emerged include qualitative improvement practices, continuous assessment, resource limitations, professional development, motivation and job satisfaction, challenges leadership and institutional support. All these themes help me in making a meaningful interpretation that directly connects to the answer of my objectives which I was drive from the participants

Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations were followed in the study before data collection. First of all teachers' permission will be obtained from their consent. Which is the part of our research after permission participants consent will be obtained from the teachers and informed about the purpose of the research. Which participants completely voluntarily will have the right to withdraw at any time without any penalty?

Participant's confidentiality will be strictly maintained. Participants name and school identity will not be mentioned in the research report with their permission and consent. To ensure participants data will be not used for other purposes just use only academic purposes and will not be shared with unauthorized individuals. Teachers' records collected on research purposes do not include personal identification details without their permission. All study information will be saved in hand and ensure no harm pressure and

discomfort is caused by any participant of the study. And ensure the privacy of all participants will be protected in this study.

Limitations

This study research restriction faces sometimes. Firstly it will be limited to Sialkot teachers' and research findings not represent all teachers' in the Pakistan context. And the second limit will be the data collected through questionnaire depend on honest response from participants of this research. Sometimes the third restriction will be to examine the score maybe influenced by other factors such as home environment or teachers' background or motivation.

1. Proposed Analysis

I tried finding form data interviews world analysed for thematic analysis to explore teacher lived experiences and perceptions regarding total quality management TQM practices in teacher education institutions in Sialkot. Several themes linked from the responses of participants reflect both the strength and challenges of TQM implementation.

Theme-1 Continuous Improvement and Quality insurance

Participants revealed that TQM as a process of continuous improvement in any institutional performance quality and teaching. Teachers highlighted that classroom practices, such as evaluations monitoring, regular assessment, as important thought of assurance of quality mechanisms. Many participants perceived that the TQM process improved accountability and institutional discipline.

One participant revealed that monitoring and feedback help to improve teaching standards and connection between administrations and teaching. Similarly some participants recognized that continuous evaluation helps to identify institutional weaknesses and improve the educational process.

Theme-2 Students Centred Teaching and Active Participation

Student centred approach already play a significant role in education point of view but according to the theme a major emerging from the finding was the importance of student engagement and participation in their classrooms.

Teachers revealed that TQM practices motivate the teachers as a leader and a helper of their class. Which leads or helps their students and engages the class with their interactive teaching methods, classroom participation, presentations, quizzes, and practical activities. Most participants behind these approaches improve students' abilities, confidence, critical thinking, analysing, and understanding, problem solving skills, and long term learning. Several participants believe that multimedia tools and practical based learning increase the students' interest and make effective classrooms learning. Teachers also revealed that regular feedback from the classroom helps to improve lesson delivering and teaching strategies.

Theme-3 Professional Development and Teacher Motivation

Teachers emphasize that professional development and teachers training very important elements of TQM. Because workshops training programs and collaboration activities are positively motivated because of this improved institutional skills and teaching quality. Many participants identified that continuous development opportunities increase their professional confidence and motivation. Teachers are so reported system evaluation, feedback improve job satisfaction and encourages them.

Theme-4 Leadership and Institutional Support

In TQM implementation leadership and institutional support a major role play. Because participants believed that support leadership strengthens coordination resources management participation highlighted that TQM implementation successfully depends on leadership and active administrative support.

Theme-5 Challenges in Implementing TQM

Server participants recognizing the benefits of TQM. But on the other hand some participants revealed the challenges affecting its implementation. So the common issue in which include lack of resources, lack of time management, infrastructure, workload pressure, excessive documentation and resistance to change. Teachers tell us heavy responsibilities for a limited time sometimes the motivated that teachers abilities that's why they do not perform or effectively apply TQM in their practices.

On the other side some participants reported that teachers are commonly unfamiliar with specific TQM concepts therefore required proper orientations and trainings.

Discussion

The finding of my study revealed that teachers generally perceived TQM as a positive framework and important element for improving education quality in teacher education institutions. Several participants strongly agree on TQM with continuous improvement, teacher centred approach, evaluation, institutional support and according to need professional development. These findings are consistent with (Khan et al., 2019) who emphasized that TQM improved when continuous improvement and teamwork will promote education institutions.

That's driving further to highlight that teacher quality influence through the monitoring system, teaching training and from students' feedback not only teaching quality in few lines but also institutional effectiveness. Similarly finding word reported by (Sajjad et al., 2021) who highlighted that damn equality and educational performance in Pakistan higher education institutions through improved TQM practices.

Some participants revealed that their experience is technology supported learning and interactive teaching methods going then outcomes based education (OBE) will be improved. Furthermore participants believe that practical activities and continue as assessment improve not just students instead improve teachers outcomes. This finding support (De Jager & Nieuwenhuis, 2005) who argued that teaching quality through student centred approaches the work of TQM strengthens.

Furthermore participants also highlighted the significant barriers to effective TQM implementation and challenges. Limited resources, lack of time, workload pressure and resistance to change including common challenges. Challenges were identified by (Saxena, 2021) who founded negatively influence on quality management systems in educational institution behind that resource limitations and excessive burden work in their field.

Another major factor which influences TQM and practices is to highlight that leadership support. Participants believe that communication

collaboration and motivation are all elements linked by leadership support. Andy's finding a line with the study of (Latif et al., 2019; Naqvi & Naz, 2025) who argued that leadership support in Pakistan Universities roleplay in the quality of quality enhancement cell in strengthening quality insurance in their practices. Overall findings revealed that TQM has significant roleplay in the educational field to improve teachers' education institutions in Sialkot. But successful implementations apply when they continue as developments institutional support provides sufficient resources and peer or leadership collaboration.

Conclusion

This study aims to explore teachers lived experiences and perceptions regarding total quality management (TQM) practices in teaching education institutions in Sialkot. These findings highlighted that participants generally perception you about TQM as a significant roleplay and effective approach to improve teaching quality student learning outcomes institutional support and professional development through training. Teachers found that several practices which linked TQM and practices basically linked classroom or monitoring, students' feedback, continuous improvement, assessment, teamwork and outcome based education (OBE)(De Jager & Nieuwenhuis, 2005). Participants identify these practices increase student participations and strength and institutional performance.

Add the same time study revealed that several challenges such as limitation resources, workload pressure, and resistance to change and insufficient leadership support. These challenges directly influenced the improvement or implementation of TQM practices reading educational institutions. The end study includes that better TQM and practices implementation required strong leadership, continuous improvement, feedback, adequate resources and active collaboration between all stakeholders. Overall participants perceived that TQM works as a philosophy not as a management system. So, the continuous improvement positively impacts teachers' education institutions in Sialkot.

Recommendations

Study recommendations based on the finding of the study basically so the following recommendations are suggested for improving TQM in teacher

education institutions. Teacher education institutions should provide regular professional improvement through training workshops programs in this way teacher understanding improves TQM and practices.

- Institutional leadership support, communication and collaboration should strengthen of TQM implementation.
- Education institution should decrease unnecessary administrative workload and pressure on teacher only can focus more on student centred teaching approach.
- Government and educational institution should provide sufficient resources improve infrastructure technology integration with teacher education institutions.
- Quality enhancement cells (QECs) should play an active role in evaluation, monitoring and teaching activity support.
- Furthermore future research include large sample and competitively study across different cities and educational setting in Pakistan.

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